
Tourism Products Based on Tourist Interest Comments on Social Media at Ujung suso Beach East luwu District, South Sulawesi Province

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ABSTRACT: This research discusses the development of tourism products on a beach tourist attraction based on comments on social media. This research is based on explanatory using interview guidelines for key informants and the base in the school holiday season in 2023. Data were analyzed using content analysis on social media Instagram and Facebook on Ujung Suso Beach. At least based on the views of visitors who emphasize that Ujung Suso Beach tends to be safe because the beach is flat and the waves are not large, the beach atmosphere is comfortable because there are many facilities for relaxing and there are many trees on the beach. With these considerations, tourism products were developed that prioritized positive responses from visitors. Tourism products developed such as beach-based tourist attractions such as the provision of banana boats, sea tours and the development of local culinary specialties made from seafood. The research confirms that visitors are eager to enjoy the beach atmosphere and more diverse tourism activities.

KEYWORDS: Product, social media, attraction, interest

INTRODUCTION

Regional development efforts are expected to provide maximum benefits for the community and the regional environment on an ongoing basis. Regional development is carried out by utilizing the potential and opportunities that exist in the region that can be managed and developed as a resource for regional development capital. To realize these ideals requires continuous struggle and implementation of planned and integrated development programs on an ongoing basis by development actors, both by government officials as development agents and the participation of the community at large, so that national development runs. Therefore, development targets are arranged in the form of a series of programs and activities that are arranged based on a priority scale so that they can and can be implemented in accordance with the capabilities of existing resources. In the implementation of national development carried out in Indonesia, it is simpler to distinguish between sectoral development and regional development. Sectoral development is the planning and realization of national development carried out based on national interests, while regional development is the planning and realization of development in accordance with the scale of development priorities at the autonomous regional level. Tourism is described as a system consisting of components that are interrelated with one another. The four components of the tourism system put forward include tourist travel, tourist markets, tourist destinations and tourism marketing (Mill and Morrison, 1985). Koen Meyers (2009) asserts that tourism is a travel activity carried out temporarily from the original place of residence to the destination area for reasons not to settle or make a living but only to fulfill curiosity, spend leisure time or holidays and other purposes. Planning something when done well will certainly provide the maximum benefit and can also minimize all unfavorable side effects. Therefore, the importance of planning in the development of tourism as an industry is none other than so that the development of the tourism industry in accordance with what has been formulated and successfully achieve the desired goals, both in terms of economic, social, cultural, and environmental aspects. Currently, in the development of tourist attractions, various approaches are taken by managers and planners to produce the best planning products and can be applied. One of the approaches in planning that is done is issue-based tourism product planning or problems. Currently, issues or problems related to tourist attractions can be taken from various sources. One source of information related to the issues being faced by managers is sourced from social media. Social media is currently very wide open to all parties. Social media participation in exploring issues or problems is through identifying comments from netizens. Netizen comments are used as the main material for identifying issues and problems at Ujung Suso Beach. With this identification process, it is expected to obtain concrete information about what should be offered to visitors at this tourist attraction. According to Mill and Morrison (1985), there are at least five main reasons for tourism planning, namely: Identify alternative approaches to: marketing, development, industry organization, tourism awareness, services and supporting activities. Adjusting to unpredictable things such as general economic conditions, demand situations and energy supply.

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Maintaining the uniqueness of: natural resources, local culture, local architecture, historical monuments and landmarks, local events and activities, parks and outdoor sports areas, etc. in tourist destinations. Creating desirable things such as: a high level of understanding of the benefits of tourism, a clear and positive impression of an area as a tourist destination, effective organization of the tourism industry, a high level of cooperation among individual operators, and other objectives. Avoidance of undesirables, such as friction and unnecessary competition between individual tourism operators, unfriendly behavior of local people towards tourists, destruction of natural and historical assets, loss of cultural identity, loss of market share, overcrowding, congestion and traffic problems, pollution, etc. Both the government and other interested parties and actors (stakeholders) need to understand these reasons in order to develop tourism as a whole. Everything related to development, marketing, services and supporting activities must be identified in accordance with the things needed in tourism planning. The planning should certainly not eliminate the uniqueness of the tourist area, namely natural scenery, cultural heritage areas, recreational parks, and others. It is expected that together, these actors can build and develop tourism elements in accordance with their respective roles, responsibilities and motivations. The elements of a tourism plan by Page (1995) are mentioned as follows:

- Natural and socio-economic environment.
- Attractions and tourism activities.
- Accommodation
- Transportation
- Institutional elements.
- Other infrastructure.
- Other tourist facilities, utilities and services.
- Domestic and international tourist markets.
- Use of tourist infrastructure by local residents.

Tourism will be realized in the presence of a supporting atmosphere and facilities, the natural and socio-economic environment and people and visitors with a variety of interests. There are five approaches to tourism planning identified by experts. Four of them were proposed by Getz (1987) and one approach was added by Page (1995). These approaches can be described as follows:

BOOSTERISM. This is a simplistic approach that sees tourism as a positive attribute for a place and its inhabitants. Objects in an environment are offered as assets for tourism development without regard to their impacts, which according to Hall (1997) is hardly a form of tourism planning. Local communities are not involved in the planning process and the carrying capacity of the area is not considered.

1. **The Economic-Industry Approach.** This approach is a very broad approach used by cities that consider tourism as an industry that can bring economic benefits together with job creation and the emergence of opportunities in development. Tourism is conceptualized under this approach as an export to the urban system, and marketing is used to attract visitors who are the highest spenders. Economic objectives take precedence over social and environmental objectives, with the main goals being the visitor experience and the level of satisfaction experienced by tourists.
2. **The Physical-Spatial Approach.** This approach is based on the geographical "land use" tradition and planners with a rational approach to urban environmental planning. Tourism can be seen within a range of contexts, but the environmental dimension is also considered as a critical issue of the carrying capacity of tourist resources within the city. Different planning strategies based on spatial principles are used here, such as clustering of visitors in key areas, or solutions to avoid over-concentration of visitors in one area, and solutions to avoid possible conflicts. However, one criticism of this approach is that it fails to consider the social and cultural impacts of urban tourism.
3. **The Community Approach.** This is an approach that emphasizes the importance of maximum involvement of the local community in the planning process. Traditional top-down planning, where planners set the agenda, needs to be modified to include the needs and desires of local communities in the planning and decision-making process. Thus, community tourism planning considers the importance of socially acceptable tourism development guidelines. This approach emphasizes the importance of social and cultural benefits for local communities together with a range of economic and environmental considerations. According to Haywood (1988), in the implementation of the plan, the "political form" of the planning process often decreases in degree for example from partnership (partnership) to appreciation (tokenism).
4. **Sustainable Approach (Sustainable tourism planning).** This approach, identified by Page, is a sustainability approach concerned with the long term future of resources and the effects of economic development on the environment which may also cause cultural and social disruption to establish individual patterns of life and lifestyles. In the context of tourism planning, sustainable development is based on several principles established by the World Commission on the Environment and Development (the Brundtland Commission) in 1987 which according to Hall (1997) relate to equity. Ujung Suso Beach is located on the east side of Lemo Beach. The condition of the beach with shallow water to the middle of the sea provides a view and safety in water activities. Lemo Beach has a stretch of tidal area that protrudes into the ocean to more than 70 meters.

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This beach is also routinely used Hindus in East Luwu district to perform the Melasti Ritual which is carried out before the Nyepi holiday celebration. In this beach area, visitors can enjoy Sunset in the afternoon and when in the early period of the year can generally be seen sunrise on the cape on this beach. Located in Mabonta Village, Burau District, East Luwu Regency, and South Sulawesi Province. Tourist activities that are usually done by tourists are swimming, taking selfies, playing swings, watching sunset and sunrise. Existing tourist facilities consist of: Gazebos, toilets, bathrooms, food and beverage vendors, photo spots. Public facilities available consist of: Parking, food and beverage stalls. It is recommended to visit this place in the morning before 10 am and in the afternoon after 4 pm. Ujung Suso Beach has an elongated coastal land contour, overgrown by many coconut plants that are quite dense along the coast and overgrown with shrubs and mangroves. Ujung Suso Beach Tourism in East Luwu, South Sulawesi is one of the tourist attractions located in Mabonta, Burau, East Luwu Regency, South Sulawesi, Ujung Suso Beach Tourism Object in East Luwu, South Sulawesi is a tourist spot that is visited on weekdays and holidays. Ujung Suso Beach has an elongated coastal plain contour, overgrown by coconut plants along the coast, and there are supporting facilities and infrastructure for tourists such as Warung Wakan, public toilets, Gasebo. Water depth is a fairly important aspect that is taken into account in determining an area to be used as a beach tourism area, especially bathing and swimming because it greatly affects the safety aspects when swimming. Physically shallow water depth is good enough to be used as a bathing and swimming recreation object.

DISCUSSION

The results of the research measuring the depth of the waters of Ujung Suso Beach, the depth of the water is relatively shallow and good to be used for marine beach tourism objects in the recreation category, especially bathing and swimming, with a good depth ranging from 0-3 meters. Ujung Suso Beach has the characteristics of an average depth of 2 meters so it can be concluded that Ujung Suso Beach is very suitable. The researchers concluded that the depth of the waters of Ujung Suso Beach is very safe for marine tourism activities in the recreational category, especially bathing and swimming, this is in accordance with the opinion of (Hazeri, 2014) which provides a limit to the depth value for the suitability of depth for recreational beach tourism and swimming is quite suitable between 3-6 meters. Based on observations in the field, the width of Ujung Suso Beach is very suitable to be used as a marine tourism object because Ujung Suso Beach has a sloping beach where tourists who come to Ujung Suso Beach can play sand, play waves on the beach. The width of Ujung Suso Beach >10 according to Yulianda (2007) is very suitable (S1) if it is used as an area for recreational beach tourism. Brightness is a measure of the transparency of the waters, which is determined visually using a secchi disk, the brightness value is expressed in units of meters. This value is greatly influenced by weather conditions, the time of measurement of turbidity and suspended solids, and the accuracy of the person taking the measurement. A tourist attraction must increase its competitive advantage in tourism development. Michael E. Porter (2008) states that competitive advantage requires building factors such as:

- a. **Cost Advantages:** The advantage of the costs that must be incurred in the provision of tourism products and services is an important factor in building the competitive advantage of tourism destinations. It incorporates various factors that can develop destination performance such as planning (design); tourism product development; marketing; service; and price. In the context of government, cost advantage can also be assisted by the harmonization of regulations between the central and local governments related to financial incentives, tariff setting and taxation or levy schemes.
- b. **Differentiation:** Differentiating tourism destinations and products is the focus in developing tourism comparative advantage. A tourism destination must be able to be different from its competitors when producing unique and valuable accessibility, attractions and amenity for incoming tourists. Differentiation is not merely done by offering lower prices for products and services.
- c. **Business Linkages:** Developing mutually beneficial relationships is an integrative process in building tourism's competitive advantage. The relationships built are vertical and horizontal and are integrated with each other.
- d. **Services:** Consistent services since tourists arrive at the entry point, while in tourism destinations until their return. All related parties such as hotel employees, the community, taxi drivers and others should be able to provide excellent and standard services so as to leave a deep impression on tourists.
- e. **Infrastructures:** The condition of tourism supporting infrastructure and facilities that are well maintained and operated is also an important factor in building the competitive advantage of a tourism destination.
- f. **Technology:** The use of appropriate and easy-to-use technology will be able to provide support for services to tourists who come besides being able to also support the decision-making process in the development, management and marketing of tourism destinations.
- g. **Human Resources:** The competence of human resources for tourism services and development is an important key to the implementation of the various factors forming the competitive advantage mentioned above. The various factors forming competitive advantage illustrate the complexity of tourism development that is multisectoral and multidisciplinary for the central, provincial and local levels. However, to implement it successfully, three important elements are needed: a) Vision; b)

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Leadership; and c) Commitment. These three elements must also be demonstrated in the process of developing, managing and marketing tourism. Especially at the central level, the implementation of the three elements mentioned above has been proven by the issuance of Presidential Instruction Number 16 of 2005 concerning Culture and Tourism Development Policy.

In The Existing Conditions, Opportunities for Tourism Product Development at Ujung Suso Beach Can Be Divided Into Several

Types:

1. Natural tourism products developed at Ujung Suso Beach and its surroundings in the future are directly related to the characteristics of the coastal area. A number of natural tourism products that will be developed are: Swimming activities at sea and beach. Swimming activities are mostly carried out in the western coastal area. Swimming activities are carried out by utilizing sea water with the help of tools / boats / buoys used by visitors. Activities can be carried out either by swimming or using tools.
2. Artificial tourism products that will be developed are more directed towards the use of technology in the implementation of tourism activities. A number of artificial tourism activities that will be developed:
 - a. watersport tourism activities. This activity is generally in the form of banana boat, canoying. Development of watersport products is expected to be entirely at sea.
 - b. Culinary tourism based on sea ingredients. This culinary also emphasizes the aspirations of the community regarding the need to provide typical culinary at Ujung Suso Beach so that visitors can enjoy it.
 - c. Event-based tourism. This event-based tourism activity consists of: water tourism events, music events, thematic festival events (modern art, sports, etc.), New Year events, coastal village events, youth events, agricultural events, culinary events, fisheries and marine events, agricultural events.
 - d. Coastal camping. Coastal camping activities are carried out in the beach area. Visitors can enjoy camping by using tents or using hammocks tied between existing trees.
 - e. Selfie spot. Selfie spots are built on the east side of the beach, Selvie spots will be used by visitors using different themes both cartoon themes, coastal themes and themes of daily activities.
 - f. Swing. Swing is developed by utilizing coconut tree trunks. Swing will be built as many as 3 points. The view offered for swing visitors is the view of the open sea.
 - g. Icon of Ujung Suso Beach. The development of the Ujung Suso Beach icon will be carried out 4 times in the period 2021, 2023, 2025 and 2027. Icon development will have its own theme every 2 years such as the construction of icons made from wood, icons made from woven bamboo, icons made from woven coconut and icons made from plastic waste.

IMPLICATION

This tourism product planning is solely based on visitor comments on social media Facebook and Instagram. A number of tourism products that are offered emphasize the potential elements that exist at the location. The utilization of trees, calm water conditions and a wide stretch of beach are used as materials for developing tourism products. This approach allows developing tourist attractions that are considered aspirational. The general impact of this planning step is that it requires handling the authenticity of the location so that the distinctive character of the tourist attraction that made people come to visit in the first place is not lost.

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